

A SYSTEM OF INDICATORS (BSC) THAT BALANCES THE QUALITY OF SERVICES IN
THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: our thesis analyzes the importance of the balanced scorecard (BSC) in managing the quality of services in the context of sustainable development. The BSC system is considered an effective tool for improving service quality, achieving strategic goals, and ensuring the long-term sustainable development of the organization. The main areas of this system - financial indicators, customer satisfaction, internal business processes and personnel, and innovations - serve for a comprehensive assessment and improvement of the quality of service. Also, the BSC supports the principles of sustainable development and provides balanced management of the organization's development in environmental, economic, and social aspects.

Keywords: balanced scorecard (BSC), service quality, sustainable development, financial indicators, customer satisfaction, internal business processes, personnel, and innovations, strategic management.

Annotatsiya: tezisimizda barqaror rivojlanish sharoitida xizmatlar sifatini boshqarishda muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimining (BSC) ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. BSC tizimi xizmat sifatini yaxshilash, strategik maqsadlarga erishish va tashkilotning uzoq muddatli barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda samarali vosita sifatida qaraladi. Mazkur tizimning asosiy yo'nalishlari – moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar, mijozlar qoniqishi, ichki biznes jarayonlari va kadrlar hamda innovatsiyalar – xizmat ko'rsatish sifatini kompleks baholash va takomillashtirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, BSC barqaror rivojlanish tamoyillarini qo'llab-quvvatlab, tashkilotning ekologik, iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy jihatlar bo'yicha rivojlanishini muvozanatli boshqarishni ta'minlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: muvozanatlashgan ko'rsatkichlar tizimi (BSC), xizmatlar sifati, barqaror rivojlanish, moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar, mijozlar qoniqishi, ichki biznes jarayonlari, kadrlar va innovatsiyalar, strategik boshqaruv.

Аннотация: в тезисе анализируется важность системы сбалансированных показателей (BSC) в управлении качеством услуг в контексте устойчивого развития. Система BSC считается эффективным инструментом повышения качества обслуживания, достижения стратегических целей и обеспечения долгосрочного устойчивого развития организации. Основные направления этой системы – финансовые показатели, удовлетворенность клиентов, внутренние бизнес-процессы и персонал и инновации – служат для комплексной оценки и улучшения качества обслуживания. Также BSC поддерживает принципы устойчивого развития и обеспечивает сбалансированное управление развитием организации с точки зрения экологического, экономического и социального аспектов.

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Ключевые слова: сбалансированная система показателей (BSC), качество обслуживания, устойчивое развитие, финансовые показатели, удовлетворенность клиентов, внутренние бизнес-процессы, персонал и инновации, стратегический менеджмент.

Introduction. Sustainable development is important for ensuring long-term success for organizations. Therefore, the balanced scorecard (BSC) in service quality management is an effective management tool for strategic planning and monitoring results.

The balanced scorecard (BSC) is a comprehensive management model used to ensure the achievement of the organization's strategic goals. This system takes into account not only the financial, but also non-financial aspects of the organization, harmonizing them with each other.

Analysis and results. The main essence of the balanced scorecard (BSC) is as follows:

1. Adaptability to strategic goals. BSC serves to link the organization's long-term strategic plans and daily operational activities. Each indicator is aimed at achieving the overall goal of the organization. The BSC system provides flexible management of the organization's strategic goals. Based on this system, the overall goals and objectives of the organization are linked to the daily activities of each department, team and employee. Thus, the organization ensures that its strategy is understood and implemented uniformly at all levels.

One of the main features of the balanced scorecard's adaptability to strategic goals is the linking of strategy with operational activities, that is, the system translates strategic goals into real activities and monitors them through measurable indicators. The second feature is flexible planning. In this case, strategic goals can change as market conditions, customer needs, or technological developments change. BSC helps to quickly adapt to these changes. Consistency at all levels of the organization is also a feature of the balanced scorecard's adaptability to strategic goals, and activities are carried out in accordance with strategic goals, from top management to lower-level employees.

The advantage of the balanced scorecard's adaptability to strategic goals is that it focuses on key goals through optimal resource allocation. In this case, employee activities are linked to strategic directions, which increases the likelihood of achieving overall goals and ensures the coherence of short-term tasks and long-term strategic plans.

Figure 1-2. Stacking up alternative development scenarios for city (A) in different study times (Y1) and (Y2).

Thus, flexibility in strategic goals provides the organization with greater clarity, efficiency and consistency in implementing its strategy, which increases competitiveness and allows it to achieve sustainable development.

2. Multidimensional approach, in which the system does not limit the organization's activities only to financial indicators, but covers the following four main areas:

- financial indicators, measuring the economic results and financial stability of the organization;
- customer satisfaction, meeting customer needs and the level of satisfaction from them;
- internal business processes, evaluating internal processes to improve the efficiency of operations;
- personnel and innovation, monitoring employee skills, growth opportunities and innovative activities.

One of the main advantages of the balanced scorecard (BSC) system is a multidimensional approach that analyzes the organization's activities from different perspectives. This approach covers not only financial indicators, but also other important aspects that affect the success of the organization. This approach ensures balance and integration across all areas of the organization's operations.

3. Results-oriented. BSC not only monitors performance indicators, but also allows you to analyze where the organization is developing. The system helps to strategically determine the directions of the organization's development. The BSC system focuses all the activities of the organization on achieving strategic results. In this approach, not the processes themselves are important, but the results obtained from them. Each indicator of the system is clearly measurable and serves to ensure results that correspond to the main goals of the organization.

Results-oriented is one of the central principles of the BSC system, linking the organization's activities with results and facilitating the achievement of common goals. This approach increases efficiency and contributes to the successful implementation of the strategy.

Figure 3. The research model is developed based on literature research to support the hypothesis.

4. Support for the principles of sustainable development. The BSC system uses the principle of ensuring the sustainable development of organizations by integrating environmental, economic and social issues.

The balanced scorecard (BSC) helps the organization implement strategies that correspond to the principles of sustainable development. Sustainable development is aimed at ensuring the long-term success of an organization by combining three main areas - environmental, economic and social sustainability.

Research has shown that the balanced scorecard (BSC) system increases the economic efficiency of the organization, protects the environment and ensures social responsibility by supporting the principles of sustainable development.

Conclusions and recommendations. Through this approach, the organization serves to create value not only for the present, but also for future generations.

The balanced scorecard (BSC) system is a powerful management tool for strategic management of the organization's activities, increasing efficiency and ensuring sustainable development. It defines single goal-oriented indicators for all parts of the organization and through them guides the implementation of strategic plans.

The BSC system is a universal tool aimed at improving the quality of services and helps organizations achieve strategic goals, meet customer needs and adapt to sustainable development. This system ensures not only financial efficiency, but also overall sustainable development.

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